

Chemistry—Indian Scenario and the Indian Chemical Society†

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I am grateful to all the Fellows of the Indian Chemical Society who elected me to the exalted office of the President of the Indian Chemical Society which has been adored by great luminaries beginning with Sir Prafulla Chandra Ray, a pioneer in the field of chemical education and research in this country of whom another illustrious President of the Society (Late) Professor J. N. Mukherjee had rightly said, "outweighing his achievements as a scientific worker, the creation and fostering of an Indian School of Chemistry will ever remain his conspicuous contribution towards national progress of Indians". On this occasion I pay my respectful homage to this great Master. By bestowing this great honour to me my fellow members of the Society have put on me a heavy responsibility but I wonder to what extent I will be able to fulfil their hopes and aspirations despite my best intentions and efforts due to limitations of various sorts and hindrance from certain quarters. But I am confident that with the help and cooperation of the majority it may be possible to make a move in the forward direction. I therefore expect my fellow members to come forward with concrete suggestions and constructive criticisms for improvement in the functioning of our organisation that is surely dear to our heart.

The Indian Chemical Society is now in the 65th year of its existence and it is high time that we do as little bit of stock-taking regarding our success as well as our failures in achieving the aims and objectives of its illustrious founders and in fulfilling our obligations to the Indian community in general and its scientific community in particular.

Chemistry had its origin in man's endeavour to provide the arts and comforts of life. Indeed science as specialised knowledge is of little relevance unless its application does any good to humanity. The value of any scientific research is best judged by the part it plays in the promotion of human welfare, and chemistry has played a very vital role in the progress and prosperity of human race and advancement of our civilisation. But unfortunately it has also been responsible in our time in bringing miseries to mankind because of indiscriminate and ill-designed applications.

But despite this position it is very true, as the Nobel Laureate G. T. Seaborg had said, "Just as middle ages man could not ignore the church, nor renaissance man the arts,.....so modern man cannot

ignore science" —and this is particularly true of chemistry. There are innumerable examples that scientific discoveries which brought untold miseries to human race later put to good use in the service of mankind, as it actually happened with nuclear energy, or with some of the chemical weapons of war like the nerve gases which are now finding application in cancer therapy. Members of the chemical community in several developed countries of the world have in recent years expressed strongly against utter abuse of chemical knowledge. They have also made plans and programmes to create an awareness among the common man regarding both the brighter and darker aspects of chemistry.

The Chemical Societies of such developed countries also fulfil their social obligations in various other ways. For the purpose of dissemination of knowledge they organise symposia, workshops, conferences, etc. at national and international levels, apart from bringing out journals in which research findings are published after rigorous scrutiny to ensure quality and credibility of the publications. These societies thus effectively serve the cause of science, the scientific community and the nation. Obviously they are therefore able to attract most of the scientific workers in their country, both in the industries and the institutions. They are also responsible for a close interaction between science and technology which synergistically helps both science and technology to develop. In contrast, we do very little indeed to justify the existence of our Society nor have we been able to consolidate ourselves into a position of authority that our views are sought and honoured by different agencies and organisations in this country in vital decision-making in the field of chemical science such as in making several coveted awards and bestowing honours and recognitions.

We hold this Annual Convention of Chemists, but of late this has become more of a ritual. The Journal of the Indian Chemical Society which we publish is far behind the level of our expectation in quality and in all other respect. We are all aware of this lamentable position but unfortunately we have only to blame ourselves primarily for the present state of affairs.

Today chemistry encompasses a very wide field covering a diversity of knowledge. Hence, on truly academic considerations holding of smaller meetings with like-minded people as participants can be

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much more purposeful than holding of a convention of the sort we are organising at present. It was with this intention and purpose that in the early seventies, when I was the Hony. Secretary of the Society, I got approved through the Council a proposal for creating Divisions in different subject areas in the Society, as they have in many other Chemical Societies of the world, to promote activities in specialised areas. Despite this position my successors did not take steps for its implementation. In fact, it has now become a sort of tradition in our country that every time with a change in the personnel the earlier decisions are abandoned and even reversed at times. The result is that there is no continuity of efforts and nothing tangible is achieved. Even in planning the scientific activities of the Convention we do not show much prudence and many a times even decisions of the Convention Committee and of other policy making bodies are grossly ignored. I strongly feel that instead of holding parallel scientific sessions in conventional areas we should arrange discussions in a few well-defined areas. In fact, discussions need not be held every year in the same areas, rather we should select a few areas every year as may be considered important in the current context. In addition, we must also think of holding smaller micro-symposia type meetings at different regions under the auspices of the branches of the Society or of groups with active participation of a limited number of persons working in the areas of concern for a more fruitful interaction.

Chemistry is a branch of physical science having a long history. Science is systematic knowledge; the purpose of scientific research is advancement of the boundaries of knowledge and its aim is establishment of truth. Credibility and ethics are two of the most essential qualities of a civilised man and this is more particularly true for any one engaged in the pursuit of science. However, of late there has been considerable erosion of sense of values and I am sorry to point out that credibility and ethics are sadly lacking among the members of our scientific community in general. The developments in the Society during the last few years which are still fresh in our memory well illustrate this point. It is indeed a pity that genuine complaints of a serious nature regarding gross acts of nepotism and favouritism, and denying even the minimum rightful dues to the deserving persons levelled against the king-makers in science in this country are hushed up or go unattended. This is extremely demoralising and it has vitiated the scientific temper in the country to such an extent that the conditions are far from being conducive for science to flourish. In a state of utter frustration many of our promising young men switch on to the cheaper and easier methods of gaining benefits by acting as sycophants of the influential group. Unfortunately, the present-day conditions in India are such that those engaged in unethical practices are not considered unethical, but who raise their voice in protest are branded as unethical.

In the words of Michael Faraday, "The scientist should be a man willing to listen to every suggestion, but determined to judge for himself. He should not be biased by appearances, have no favourite hypothesis, be of no school, and in doctrine have no master. He should not be a respecter of persons but of things. Truth should be his primary object". I wonder how many members of our community possess these qualities.

Promotion of human welfare is one of the most tangible objectives of scientific endeavour. Jawaharlal Nehru had once said, "For a hungry man or a hungry woman, truth has little meaning, we have to find for them all the absolute necessities of life". But despite this position it is essential to support science in the fullest measure. Although the cultural and intellectual aspects of basic research are not well appreciated this can hardly be undermined. And for basic research to flourish it needs an appropriate environment, and adequate financial and administrative support. Unfortunately, there is a tendency among decision-makers now a days to give far less priority to basic research. But it is basic research alone which widens the horizon of knowledge that makes a strong base for applied research to flourish as well, since it is basic research which to the highest degree develops the human faculties to solve a wide range of problems. However, basic research has to be of a high quality which encourages innovativeness, and judged in this context what is now going on in most institutions can hardly be considered relevant to science in any form. Any scrutiny of the papers which have been contributed for the Annual Convention of Chemists held during the last several years would amply prove this point. Most of the presentations do have little impact, if any, on the advancement of science. As far as research in chemistry is concerned the Indian Chemical Society can play a major role by imposing adequate safeguards against presentation and publication of papers which are not up to the mark in scientific content and quality.

As is true of any creative human enterprise basic research can flourish only around a few really competent and talented individuals whose efforts must be supported without hindrance. However, the present-day trend for so-called democratic management of institutions and research laboratories, where all are considered equal, is hardly conducive for the development of excellence in science. The academic freedom enjoyed by the members of the faculty of some Indian universities in the pre-independent and also for more some time in the post-independent periods was to a great extent helpful for academic excellence in these institutions. But in recent years under the banner of assumed equality and a sense of respect for fake democracy conditions have become far less conducive for development of excellence at these centers. The Government has much responsibility in the matter as it frames rules and regulations for the administration of the universities. In the

name of democracy decision-making bodies in the universities have been filled with men having very little interest, far less knowledge and expertise, for assessing needs for academic development and making suitable plans and adopting suitable policies for the purpose of any real development in absolute terms. It is also necessary to express boldly that higher education is not meant for the masses, and is only for the most deserving few. But in our country floodgates have been opened for everybody to throng the universities and all this has been done out of our false sense of vanity for spreading higher education. The undue haste in our attempt to impart higher education in regional languages also requires serious consideration as to its desirability and feasibility. It is indeed meaningless to talk about the conditions in Japan or the Soviet Union where the situations are very different. Excellence often meets with a casualty due to the envy and jealousy of the far less competent majority, and due to petty considerations of organised individuals and groups. Those in administrative control of our institutions must recognise that excellence in research can only flourish around some gifted persons and the groups working under their dynamic leadership and for this we do need an environment which is not the environment of the factories nor of the Government offices. Both the grant-giving agencies such as the UGC and the university administration should realise that activities of such individuals and small groups need to be adequately supported despite the fact that their specific requirements may not be at all a requirement of the majority of the other faculty members whose interests may be very different or they may not have any interest at all as is also true quite often. The universities in general do not have good facilities for the maintenance and upkeep of costly equipments which require regular attention and servicing. As a result whatever is purchased with all the meagre grants received remains inoperative most of the time.

It is indeed a pity that the universities which are supposed to be the temples for advancement of learning have now been totally crippled by undue political interventions, group rivalry, academic nepotism, unionism, etc and are also grossly ill-equipped both in terms of equipment, library and workshop facilities and quality of teachers and hence lacking the necessary infrastructure for the cultivation and promotion of modern science. The future of science and technology certainly depends on the quality of manpower which the universities are supposed to provide. In the words of the great visionary Sir Asutosh Mookerjee, "The University is a great store-house of learning, a great bureau of standards, a great workshop of knowledge, a great laboratory for the training as well as men of thought as men of action. The University is thus the instrument of the state for the conservation of knowledge, for the discovery of knowledge, for the distribution of knowledge, for the application

of knowledge, and above all, for the creation of knowledge makers". Hence, in the interest of the nation we must make an all out effort to remove the maladies such that the universities are able to provide a strong ground for science to develop and are able to turn out trained people who have the awareness, capability as well as the foresight to help the nation in its forward march to an all round success. Science is the ultimate source of strength, power and prosperity of a nation, and this is particularly true of chemistry.

Academic excellence cannot develop in an institution under government control and for this autonomy of the universities in the real sense is most essential. In this connection it is worth noting that when in the year 1922 the then Government sanctioned a handsome grant to the Calcutta University with an imposed condition that accounts be submitted to the Government, our illustrious predecessors boldly expressed themselves and what Sir P. C. Ray, then Sir Tarak Nath Palit Professor and Head of the Department of Chemistry, Calcutta University, said in a Senate Meeting is indeed very illuminating: "There is an unseen hand working from behind with dark and sinister purposes...I think we had better shown a bold front...the conditions are so humiliating, so gallantly derogatory to our self-respect, that we had better close down the concern, lock up the gates of the University...A grave crisis is looming large in the horizon...so it behoves us to take concerted action and try our best to avert the calamity; we should gird up our loins and see that the noble heritage which has been granted to us is not bartered for a mess of pottage...the lamp which we have been able to light so very dimly, so that it might burn up brilliantly, is about to be extinguished...We shall not go down on our knees. We are not to cry *peccavi*. We are not charity boys. We are not Oliver Twists".

In deep contrast, we see today that members of our so-called academic community are running to politicians so that there may be firmer control of our Alma Mater by the political party in power and of men of their choice. I wonder at the approaching evening of my career what is in store for our successors and descendants. It is worth remembering what Jawaharlal Nehru had said regarding the purpose of the University, "The University stands for humanism, for reason, for the adventure of ideas and for search of truth. It stands for the onward march of the human race towards even higher objectives".

However, it is necessary to bear in mind that no amount of reform only at the University level alone would be adequate and changes must be made from the elementary stage. Schools and colleges need to be strengthened such that scientific temper may inculcate the young minds and they develop an interest and attitude to science. The future of chemistry and of science in general will depend on

our ability to attract the best quality of our young men to scientific pursuits and in this respect the professional bodies such as the Indian Chemical Society have a major role to play.

While the need to support basic research cannot be over emphasised, it is necessary to remember that basic research consumes wealth which in turn is generated by technology and this latter develops with the aid of science; hence, this is a cyclic process. While basic research should be a major activity in the universities for the training of students and for the advancement of knowledge, the training can become much more realistic and socially relevant and benefit both the students and the nation if the applications of the knowledge are also kept in mind in the selection of research problems, although each and every research problem need not be problem-oriented. The existing Ph.D. programme in the universities is far from being satisfactory as the investigations undertaken are

mostly imitative, meaningless and even at times phoney and are therefore not at all suited to create the inquisitiveness in the students or in developing their faculties to the extent that they may become problem-solvers. Our Society need to think seriously of this state and may perhaps organise seminars, symposia, workshops, etc. to discuss such issues critically so as to be able to evolve methods for an all round improvement of the doctoral programmes in chemistry and also perhaps help to identify areas of research in chemistry as may be relevant to science and the society in the present time.

While I do not expect everybody to agree with all my views I do hope that all the chemists in the country should think seriously as to how to upgrade effectively the standard of our scientific research and create an environment in this country which is conducive to science, an environment which is totally lacking at present.